

Solvent Effect on Polarographic Reduction of 3-Nitroacenaphthenequinone Oxime

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The polarographic behavior of 3-nitroacenaphthenequinone oxime has been studied in the pH range 3–10, in water, aqueous methanol, methoxyethanol and isopropanol. A strong interaction between NHOH (the first reduction product of nitro group) and C=N groups is noticed in acid solution.

The polarographic reduction of an aromatic compound is effected by a reducible substituent present in it, sometimes in a manner¹ other than the one predicted by linear free energy relations². The reduction of nitrobenzene in aqueous solution is greatly effected by the presence of organic co-solvents³. Rabindranath and Rao⁴ reported the polarographic reduction of *m*-nitroacetophenone oxime in presence of different organic solvents. Here we report the polarographic reduction of 3-nitroacenaphthenequinone oxime in water, aqueous methanol, methoxyethanol and isopropanol in the pH range 3–10.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms were recorded on a CL25 Elico DC pen recording polarograph in Britton-Robinson buffers.

Reduction at pH 3–5 : It is seen from the data (Tables 1 and 2) that one wave is observed in aqueous organic media in contrast to two waves in pure water medium. The second wave in pure aqueous solution may be due to the non-Faradaic transformation product of the species formed in the reduction of nitro group in the first wave or due to the reduction of protonated azomethine group. Based on the position of the wave on voltage axis, we believe that the second wave is not due to reduction of either the nitro group or the azomethine group, but is a result of their mutual interaction. The absence of the second wave in aquo-organic solvents, therefore, clearly suggests the presence of mutual interaction between NHOH and C=N to an extent of even eliminating the second wave. The shift in the half-wave potential of the first wave with change of organic solvent suggests that the shift is dependent on the proton-donating ability of the organic co-solvent, which is expected to be in the order : methanol-methoxyethanol > isopropanol. The splitting of the first wave at pH 3.3 in 50% aquo-methanol can be traced⁵ to different rates of uptake of the first, second and last two electrons by nitro group, its reduction to the hydroxylamine stage.

Reduction at pH 8–10 : Two waves occur in all media at pHs 6.90 and 8.20 (Fig. 1). At pH 8.20 two waves are observed in pure water medium and in 50% aqueous methanol. Nitro group does not show a wave correspond-

ing to reduction of NHOH in alkaline medium since phenylhydroxylamine is stabilized. Hence the second wave

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 3-nitroacenaphthenequinone oxime at pH 8.2 : (a) aqueous medium, (b) 50% aq. methanol, (c) 50% aq. methoxyethanol and (d) 50% isopropanol.

can only be due to the reduction of the azomethine group. It is therefore inferred that addition of organic solvent completely eliminates the mutual interaction observed in pure aqueous alkaline solution. This may perhaps be due to the greater stabilization of the hydroxylamine in these media.

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS ($-E_{1/2}$, V vs SCE) OF THE REDUCTION OF 3-NITROACENAPHTHENE QUINONE OXIME IN AQUEOUS AND AQUO-ORGANIC MEDIA AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

pH	First wave				Second wave			
	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)
3.30	0.61	0.83	0.92	0.98	1.54	—	—	—
4.20	0.64	0.81	0.94	0.97	1.50	—	—	—
5.20	0.68	0.91	0.94	0.95	1.62	—	—	—
6.20	0.77	0.81	0.95	0.94	1.66	1.40	1.45	—
7.00	0.98	0.98	0.92	0.96	1.54	1.33	1.40	1.47
8.20	0.81	0.91	0.98	0.99	1.99	1.33	1.39	1.40
9.20	0.84	0.91	1.22	1.23	1.96	1.20	—	—
10.20	0.82	0.93	1.21	1.24	1.96	1.20	—	—

(I) = Pure water, (II) = 50% aq. methanol, (III) = 50% aq. methoxyethanol, (IV) = 50% aq. isopropanol.

TABLE 2—WAVE HEIGHTS (μ_A) OF THE REDUCTION WAVES OF 3-NITROACENAPHTHENE QUINONE OXIME IN AQUEOUS AND AQUO-ORGANIC MEDIA AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

pH	First wave				Second wave			
	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)
3.30	3.6	2.3	3.4	4.2	6.2	—	—	—
4.20	3.5	3.5	3.6	4.1	6.0	—	—	—
5.20	3.5	3.9	3.8	3.8	6.0	—	—	—
6.20	3.4	2.9	2.7	3.4	4.3	1.97	1.80	—
7.00	3.6	2.5	2.3	2.2	2.1	2.20	1.91	3.60
8.20	3.5	2.2	1.91	1.75	5.8	2.40	2.41	3.00
9.20	3.5	1.81	3.7	4.5	5.7	2.9	—	—
10.20	3.4	1.65	3.1	5.0	4.1	3.1	—	—

(I) = Pure water, (II) = 50% aq. methanol, (III) = 50% aq. methoxy ethanol, (IV) = 50% aq. isopropanol.

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